

Evaluation of the Sedative Effect of Limonene to Reduce Stress During Transportation of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*)

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Abstract

Reducing stress during common aquaculture practices such as transportation is essential for improving animal welfare and aquaculture productivity. This study assessed the sedative effect of limonene, a key component of citrus essential oils, in a 6 h transport simulation of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*), including four experimental groups: (i) nontransported, (ii) control (without treatment), (iii) ethanol (with ethanol), and (iv) limonene (30 µL/L dissolved in ethanol). After transport, the slightly reduced O₂ consumption observed in the limonene group could be indicative of a reduced metabolism supported by a significant increase of chloride levels concerning other transported groups and an increase of sodium ions in fish treated with limonene. The increase of cortisol in transported groups supports its use as a good marker of acute-stress response in fish transport, showing a smaller increase in fish treated with limonene. This fact, together with the significantly reduced glucose and increased triglycerides in plasma, and the reduced expression of stress-related genes in the head kidney, may suggest a more relaxed state in fish treated with limonene. Since the sedative benefits of limonene were partly masked by the negative effects of ethanol, finding an alternative solvent could enhance its potential as a sedative for fish transport.